

E-BANKING: A STUDY ON PRACTICES AND AWARENESS IN HONNAVAR TALUK

Dr. Prasad Mahale*¹, Dr. C.K Hebbar*²

*¹Assistant Professor, Institute Of Management And Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore,
Karnataka, India.

*²Research Guide, Institute Of Management And Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore,
Karnataka, India.

ABSTRACT

Present modern world moving towards cashless banking and now a day's maximum number of banks are allowing their customers to conduct their transaction through E-banking. This is an internet based payment system that gives access to the customer system, to perform a range of financial transaction through their websites. Our study is based on E-banking practices and awareness in Honnavar talluk especially private sector commercial banks.

Keywords: E-Banking, Practices, Awareness, IMPS, Internet.

I. INTRODUCTION

Now a day's maximum number of banks are allowing their customers to conduct their transaction through E-banking. From the banks point of view E-banking reduces the costs compare to the traditional banking system. Improvement in information technology the banks can easily adopt e-banking in their system. This e-banking system allows the customers to perform traditional functions like withdrawal, deposits, checking account history and many other bank related activities without visiting to the bank premises. At present E-banking is popularizing in Honnavar talluk especially private sector commercial banks. People also slowly transforming to the e-banking products.

E-Banking:

E-banking is also known as internet banking, online banking, virtual banking etc... This is an internet based payment system that gives access to the customer system, to perform a range of financial transaction through their websites.

Objectives of the study:

This paper is mainly prepare to the following objectives

1. To understand the different services , which the banks provide under e-banking
2. To assess the changes in the practices of customers towards e-banking
3. To grasp the awareness of customers towards e-banking
4. To find out the limitations and speculate some suggestions to improvisation of e-banking.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The information or data presented in this paper is collected from both the primary method as well as secondary method Primary data is collected from a structured questionnaire to the 100 respondents who are randomly selected. Secondary data is collected through various, magazines, journals and official websites of banks.

Various services of e-banking:

1. NEFT
2. RTGS
3. IMPS
4. Internet banking
5. Mobile wallets
6. Mobile apps

1. NEFT (National Electronic Fund Transfer)

It is a internet based payment system introduced by Indian banks, which facilitates one to oOne fund transfer. It also helps to transfer funds from one bank to another bank, which takes place in batches. The batches are settled in hourly time slots

2. RTGS (Real Time Gross Settlement)

It is also an internet based payment system. In RTGS, RTGS enabled bank can send funds to another RTGS enabled banks as well as NEFT enabled banks.

3. IMPS(Immediate Payment Service)

This system is launched on 22nd November 2010 by Smt. Sharada Gopinath DG, RBI. In this system, the funds can be transfer to one bank account to another bank account through mobiles

4. Internet banking :

It is an online banking system. This is a facility which offers just about every services available by a local branch which includes deposits, withdrawals etc. With the help of internet enabled gadgets.

5. Mobile wallets :

Nowadays some software companies are providing mobile wallets for example Pay-tm, Bhim app, Chiller app, free charge etc... It is like a bank account we can make payments and transfer in mobile

6. Mobile apps :

In recent years banks are creating their own applications and giving access to their customers. From this, banking is becoming easier and easy accessible.

Advantages of E-Banking:

1. Every people are generally Known about internet usage so that implementing e-banking will be very easy task.
2. Through e-banking, it is easy for the customers as well as bankers to maintain their accounts
3. E- banking indirectly support to the environment protection as it by reducing quantity of paperwork
4. The cost which will incur in e- banking will be low compared to the traditional banking system.
5. Manual errors will be less.
6. The customer can get discount, cash backs for their purchases when making payments through e-banking.

Disadvantages of E-Banking:

1. Safety and the security is one of the major drawback of e-banking
2. E banking services cannot be accessible of some type of mobile p-hones and the internet provider
3. Relation between the customers and 6the banker cannot be so effective compare to traditional banking.

III. DATA INTERPRETATION AND FINDINGS

Table 1: Awareness about e-banking products

Services	Aware	Not aware
NEFT	90%	10%
RTGS	80%	20%
IMPS	95%	05%
Internet banking	85%	15%
Mobile apps	99%	01%

This table clearly says that majority number of public aware of E-banking products in Honnavar talluk. Especially Honnavar Talluk publics are using more number of mobile phones and they are educates.

Table 2: Users of E banking

Services	Users	Not users
NEFT	95%	05%
RTGS	85%	15%
IMPS	90%	10%
Internet banking	87%	13%
Mobile apps	99%	01%

This table shows that higher number of public uses all type banking products especially RTGS, NEFT and internet banking.

Table 3: Perceptions towards E –banking

Services	Satisfied	Not satisfied
NEFT	99%	01%
RTGS	95%	05%
IMPS	80%	20%
Internet banking	85%	15%
Mobile wallets	93%	07%
Mobile apps	97%	03%

Due to less cost eco friendliness, E-banking are commonly accepted by all.

IV. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The respondents of this study is very less and information collected from the primary and secondary method is finite.
- The respondents were using services of different banks so opinion collected may be biased to some extent.
- An element of personal bias of the customers May affect the data for certain extent.
- Time constraints were the major problems to conduct the detailed study.

V. SUGGESTIONS

After analyzing the response of the respondents in Honnavar Taluk, we would like to suggest the following suggestions

- There is urgent need of creating awareness about people of Honnavar talluk.
- Technical improvements must be needed here.
- Bank should use local languages in their banking software.
- There is a need of improvements in internet connectivity standards especially in rural area.
- Safety should be given priority while making e payments
- Bank should try to remove the fear of fraud in the minds of their customers
- Number of ATMs should be increased.

VI. CONCLUSION

To conclude, deploying E-banking is a difficult task that requires both business and technology expertise. This E-banking can empower the common man to conduct his payment transactions at 24*7. There are huge no of E-banking products and it is a big challenge for banking as well as telecom services to provide internet facility to all over Honnavar talluk. This study shows the role of e banking in present scenario E-banking plays the significant role in modern banking sector. This will allows the customers to fulfill their wants in easy way as well as to utilize banking transactions in effective manner.

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] Elias, Award M. (2012), Electronic Commerce-from vision to fulfillment, 3rd Edition, Published, PHI Learning Private Limited, New Delhi.
- [2] Kumar, Ravindra and Deshpande, Manish (2012), Electronic Business, 1st edition, Published by Pacific Books International, New Delhi.
- [3] [https:// en.wikipedia.o9rg/wiki/mobile-banking](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/mobile-banking).
- [4] Jain, Yogesh, Mobile Banking: Study on Adoption and challenges in Southern Rajasthan, India, Vol. 2, Issue 4, ISSN:2278-0211 (online). www.ijird.com
- [5] Goyal, Vishal, Pandey, U.S. and Batra, Sanjay, Mobile banking in India: Practices, Challenges and Security Issues, Vol 1, No.2, ISSN:2278-3091. www.warse.org/ijatcse/info.html/.
- [6] Mishra, Sunil Kumar and sahuo, Durga Prasad, Mobile banking Adoption and Benefits Towards Customers Services, Vol. 2, Issue 1, ISSN : 2319-2526.